

MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING
JIZZAX FILIALI

**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION
TADQIQOTLARNING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI
VA RIVOJLANISH
TENDENSIYALARI:
YECHIMLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR
RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI
TO'PLAMI**

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**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
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THEORETICAL BASIS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY SKILLS THROUGH SONG VISUALISATION

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Abstract: this article examines the theoretical foundations of teaching vocabulary skills through song visualization. It examines the fundamentals of English language teaching from the perspective of vocabulary skills. It provides an overview of one effective means of teaching vocabulary—the use of musical visualizations, which optimizes all student learning activities. Techniques for using song visualizations in developing vocabulary skills in English are presented.

Key words: song visualization, lexical skills, creative skill, song material, textual aspect.

Today, innovative methods of teaching foreign languages are becoming increasingly popular, pushing traditional reliance on textbooks and dictionaries into the background. The teaching community is constantly searching for new methods of teaching foreign languages. An analysis of scientific and methodological literature and teaching aids demonstrates that song material is often used in learning English in general and vocabulary in particular, as working with this type of text offers a number of advantages.

Firstly, the use of musical creativity adds an emotionally positive dimension to the learning process and can spark interest in all students, engaging them in active learning, which significantly facilitates learning. The use of song visualizations in lessons fosters student interest in the subject being studied and increases their motivation, both in collaborative and independent English learning. Secondly, song visualizations are an excellent resource for developing and refining pronunciation and vocabulary skills, as intonation and foreign language speech, words, phrases, and sometimes even entire sentences are learned within a cultural context. Thirdly, working with song material contributes not only to the development of students' sociocultural competence but also to the development of creative skills.

However, based on an analysis of scientific and methodological literature and textbooks, work with song material is often carried out through repeated listening, mechanical translation, and memorization. With this format, the acquisition of vocabulary

material may not be sufficiently robust. Furthermore, although modern textbooks may contain a certain number of songs, it cannot always be said that the song material for vocabulary teaching was developed based on appropriate criteria and is effective.

Most language methodologists consider vocabulary to be one of the most important components in the formation and development of students' foreign language speech skills. Vocabulary, or the set of words in a language or dialect, is considered the fundamental component of the system of linguistic means that convey semantic connections. Therefore, when teaching various aspects of language, priority attention should be given to the lexical aspect. The development of lexical skills and abilities presupposes not only the consideration of formal-structural information but also knowledge of the situational, social, and contextual rules adhered to by native speakers [2, p. 287].

The development of lexical skills is always the focus of the main educational objectives at all stages of learning. Generally speaking, the structure of lexical skills includes: the sound form of a lexical unit, operations for selecting a unit, operations for combining lexical units, and a speech task. The process of developing lexical skills consists of several stages. O.S. Levitskaya writes that foreign linguists distinguish four main steps in learning vocabulary: word perception, understanding of meaning, memorization, and use in speech. Along with these stages, the assimilation of cultural, psycholinguistic, grammatical, and textual aspects occurs [3, p. 58]. In Russian teaching methods, this system is somewhat broader. Thus, A.N. Shchukin cites the following stages of the formation of lexical skills: “perception of a word (with the subsequent creation of a sound image), awareness of the meaning of a word, imitation of a word (isolated or in a sentence), designation aimed at the independent naming of objects defined by the word, combination” [1, p. 129].

Selecting vocabulary is a significant issue when determining the content of vocabulary instruction. Linguists note the following principles for selecting a minimum vocabulary: thematic relevance, frequency and prevalence, collocation, stylistic open-endedness, semantic value of the word, and word-formation value. To optimize the acquisition of the selected content, modern teachers are increasingly turning to authentic songs, which represent valuable educational material and a multifunctional teaching tool.

Many scholars note the advantages of song visualization in foreign language teaching. First of all, working with songs ensures a more robust acquisition of vocabulary and grammar, as song lyrics, thanks to their rhyme and melody, are quickly memorized and can be retained in long-term memory. Songs serve as a foundation for the development of verbal thinking and stimulate monologues and dialogic expressions, developing the ability to speak both prepared and unprepared. Songs also provide an opportunity to develop and enhance listening skills. By listening to songs, students can reinforce correct articulation of sounds and more quickly memorize the pronunciation of words.

Song material can be used at different stages of the lesson: at the initial stage for phonetic exercises, at the stage of introducing or consolidating lexical and grammatical material, for various speech skills and abilities, as well as for releasing and relieving tension and restoring students' performance.

When studying English, a song can effectively perform the following functions: communicative-stimulating, motivational-incentive, linguacultural, aesthetic-developmental, illustrative [4, p. 44].

The technique for working with song material is divided into three main stages: pre-listening, during listening, and post-listening. Pre-listening tasks include: creating a list of associations for a specific phenomenon, filling in missing words or lines, arranging lines in the correct sequence, choosing a rhyme and completing lines, finding and reading rhyming words, modifying the lyrics by replacing adjectives and adverbs with synonyms, antonyms, verb tenses, etc., writing down the beginning of a song from dictation, and completing a verse. Before performing the lyrics, students should familiarize themselves with new vocabulary.

Possible tasks while listening: pronounce rhythmic rhymes to music, sing a song and repeat the movements, arrange the verses of a song in the correct order, dictations (write down an excerpt from a verse, complete it from memory in rhyme or with minor changes; listen to an unfamiliar song and write down the words).

Possible tasks after listening: choose a suitable definition for the definition, correct errors in the text, and reflect on a topic (assigned by the teacher).

Carefully designed and well-executed song work facilitates the introduction and reinforcement of language material and promotes the development of vocabulary skills. The greatest impact of using song visualizations in English to develop students' knowledge, skills, and abilities can only be achieved through regular, comprehensive use of song visualizations and a variety of exercises.

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